

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

RENBP

(renin binding protein)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	5973 / P51606
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Levon Halabelian ¹ , Jesse Wiley ² , Gregory Cary ³ , and the Emory-Sage-SGC-JAX TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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Affiliations	¹ Structural Genomics Consortium, University of Toronto, 101 College St, Toronto, ON M5G 1L7, Canada ² Sage Bionetworks, Seattle, WA, USA ³ The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA

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Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: RENBP_11-427_BioN: N-terminally biotinylated protein.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 1.99 (rank #11180, 55.2th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 1.99 out of 5 (rank #11180, 55.2th percentile). The individual score components include 0 of 3 for genetics, and 1.99 out of 2 for genomics. A caveat regarding the genetics score is that RENBP is located on the X-chromosome, which has historically been excluded from genetic association studies. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of RENBP, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. RENBP is annotated to the GO term "regulation of blood pressure" from the Vasculature biological domain.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
1.992	11180	55.17	0	1.992

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low

confidence measures of expression. The expression of RENBP is not confidently detected in any cell type within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

REBP is a dual functional protein described below that modulates the renin-angiotensin system(1-3) and which our work identified as an element of a core proteomic module that is associated with both AD pathological progression and cognitive decline(4). In this work we describe the basic target enablement

package that we have developed for RENBP which includes purified protein, validated antibodies for use in both biochemical studies and immunohistology and an objective bioinformatic characterization. The role of RENBP in AD is speculative, but the data suggests a strong correlation that justifies further investigation. We hope the reagents we have developed will facilitate the scientific community's exploration of RENBP's role in AD pathological progression.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

REBP (Renin binding protein) is a 427 amino acid extracellular protein with two distinct and overlapping functional domains (3, 5-7). The core of the protein forms an AGE domain which is involved in the conversion of N-acetylglucosamine to N-acetylmannosamine via catalytic epimerase activity (3, 5-7). The AGE domain is largely alpha-helical in structure and functions as a homodimer in vivo (8). In addition to the AGE domain, RENBP contains an internal leucine zipper region that facilitates RENBP's second biological function as an inhibitor of the renin protease that catalyses the conversion of angiotensinogen to angiotensin I (3), which is subsequently cleaved to form angiotensin II, which functions to regulate vasoconstriction, and hence modulates blood pressure (1, 5). Reciprocally, the renin-REBP association blocks RENBP epimerase activity, limiting its role in metabolic regulation(9). The renin-REBP interaction is implicated in the regulation of hypertension, as variants of RENBP are specifically associated with hypertensive risks (10-12). Renin and RENBP are produced predominantly in the kidneys (13, 14), yet RENBP is also expressed by numerous CNS cell types, most robustly observed within neurons, as noted above in the bioinformatics work, showing both excitatory and inhibitory neurons expressing RENBP (15). The regulation of blood pressure may function to gate both oxygen and glucose to the highly metabolically active regions of the brain and could be involved in the glymphatic clearance mechanisms critical to remove debris scavenged by astrocytes and microglial cells and promote CNS homeostasis.

Consistent with the above speculation, RENBP is implicated in immune function, as it is expressed within peripheral immune cells and may regulate immune response and early life immune system development (16, 17). Additionally, RENBP was identified in a meta-GWAS study as a novel risk factor associated with both schizophrenia and bipolar disorder (18), as well as in the Han Chinese population (19). Further support for RENBP involvement in neuronal systems comes from the linkage between proteomic dysregulated pituitary axis genes in response to induction of chronic mild stress, in which RENBP dysregulation is correlated with stress-induced anxiety (20). The data is only circumstantial suggesting that regulation of stress-responsive modulation of the neurovascular unit may be associated with RENBP linkage to schizophrenia, bipolar or anxiety. However, the work by our group identified RENBP as a core member of a proteomic module linked with AD pathological progression and cognitive decline (4), both AD traits are associated with clearance mechanisms tethered to the neurovascular unit, at least mildly supporting a potential role in glial mediated clearance mechanisms through vascular coupling. The role of RENBP in AD pathological progression warrants further investigation by the scientific community which we hope will be aided by the resources provided by this project.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. RENBP_11-427_BioN: N-terminally biotinylated protein.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of RENBP in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Gene name	RENBP
Uniprot ID	P51606
Region	1-417

Description	Catalyzes the interconversion of N-acetylglucosamine to N-acetylmannosamine (PubMed: 9990133 , PubMed: 10502668 , PubMed: 12499362). Involved in the N-glycolylneuraminic acid (Neu5Gc) degradation pathway: although human is not able to catalyze formation of Neu5Gc due to the inactive CMAHP enzyme, Neu5Gc is present in food and must be degraded (PubMed: 9990133).
Synonyms	N-acylglucosamine 2-epimerase
Construct ID	RENBP_11-427_BioN PBC039A03
Parental Vector	pFBD-BirA
Tag (N-terminal)	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
Tag (C-terminal)	GGSGHHHHHH
Protein mass (with tag)	50114.06 Da

Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	98610
Protein sequence (with tag)	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGMEKERETLQAWKERVGQELDRVAF WMEHSHDQEHGGFFTCGLGREGRVYDDLKVVWLQGRQVWMYCRLYRTE RFRHAQLLDAAKAGGEFLLRYARVAPPGKKCAFVLRDGRPVKVQRTIFSEC FYTMAMNELWRATGEVRYQTEAVEMMDQIVHWVQEDASGLGRPQLQG APAAEPMAVPMMLLNLVEQLGEADEELAGKYAELGDWCARRILQHVQRD GQAVLENVSEGGKELPGCLGRQQNPGHTLEAGWFLLRHCIRKGDPELRAH VIDKFLLLPFHSGWDPDHGGLFYFQDADNFCPTQLEWAMKLWVPHSEA MIAFLMGYSDSGDPVLLRLFYQVAEYTRQFRDPEYGEWFGYLSREGKVAL SIKGGPFKGC FHVPRCLAMCEEMLGALLSRPAPAPSPAPTPACRGAEGGSG HHHHHH

Purified Protein	
IMAC affinity purification (step 1): RENBP_11-427_BioN PBC039A03	
SEC (step 2): RENBP_11-427_BioN PBC039A03	
IEC (Step 3): RENBP_11-427_BioN PBC039A03	
Intact Mass Deconvolution:	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	4.5 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	Insect cells: <i>Sf9</i> (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)
Expression Medium	I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre
Transformation and storage	The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent <i>Sf9</i> cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.
Expression	For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIIC) were prepared by infection of the <i>Sf9</i> cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of <i>Sf9</i> cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes are monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when <i>Sf9</i> cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.

<p>Purification buffers</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Wash Buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 5 mM imidazole 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 150 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 4. SEC buffer: 20 mM Tris (pH 7.5), 250 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 5. IEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 260 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 6. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
<p>Purification step 1: IMAC</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (2 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 90W output power) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (1 hour, 38400xg, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add the cleared lysate onto (1ml/L) Talon Metal Affinity Resin (Cat# 635504 Clontech) in a 250 mL canonical tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hour in a cold room. 4. Transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Wash column with 1CV of wash buffer. 7. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.

Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for next step.
Purification step 3: Ion exchange chromatography (IEX)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Source S, cation exchange chromatography. 2. Elute with concentration gradient of 20 mM tris (pH 7.5), 1 M NaCl, 2 mM TCEP (buffer B). 3. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 3 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Snap-freeze aliquots in PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

References

1. Nguyen G, Burckle C, Sraer JD. The renin receptor: the facts, the promise and the hope. *Curr Opin Nephrol Hypertens.* 2003;12(1):51-5.
2. Danser AH. Local renin-angiotensin systems: the unanswered questions. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol.* 2003;35(6):759-68.
3. Murakami K, Hirose S, Chino S, Ueno N, Miyazaki H. Properties of renin-binding protein. *Clin Exp Hypertens A.* 1982;4(11-12):2073-81.
4. Johnson ECB, Carter EK, Dammer EB, Duong DM, Gerasimov ES, Liu Y, et al. Large-scale deep multi-layer analysis of Alzheimer's disease brain reveals strong proteomic disease-related changes not observed at the RNA level. *Nat Neurosci.* 2022;25(2):213-25.
5. Takahashi S, Inoue H, Fukui K, Miyake Y. Structure and function of renin binding protein. *Kidney Int.* 1994;46(6):1525-7.
6. Takahashi S, Inoue H, Miyake Y. The human gene for renin-binding protein. *J Biol Chem.* 1992;267(18):13007-13.
7. Morris BJ. New possibilities for intracellular renin and inactive renin now that the structure of the human renin gene has been elucidated. *Clin Sci (Lond).* 1986;71(4):345-55.
8. Allard ST, Giraud MF, Naismith JH. Epimerases: structure, function and mechanism. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 2001;58(11):1650-65.
9. Takahashi S, Kumagai M, Shindo S, Saito K, Kawamura Y. Renin inhibits N-acetyl-D-glucosamine 2-epimerase (renin-binding protein). *J Biochem.* 2000;128(6):951-6.
10. Kelly TN, Li C, Hixson JE, Gu D, Rao DC, Huang J, et al. Resequencing Study Identifies Rare Renin-Angiotensin-Aldosterone System Variants Associated With Blood Pressure Salt-Sensitivity: The GenSalt Study. *Am J Hypertens.* 2017;30(5):495-501.
11. Ji LD, Li JY, Yao BB, Cai XB, Shen QJ, Xu J. Are genetic polymorphisms in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system associated with essential hypertension? Evidence from genome-wide association studies. *J Hum Hypertens.* 2017;31(11):695-8.

12. Dong Y, Ding Y, Cun Y, Xiao C. Association of renin binding protein (RnBP) gene polymorphisms with essential hypertension in the Hani minority of southwestern China. *J Genet Genomics*. 2013;40(8):433-6.
13. Takahashi S, Miura R, Miyake Y. A study on renin binding protein (RnBP) in the human kidney. *J Biochem*. 1985;97(2):671-7.
14. Leckie BJ, Lacy PS, Lidder S. The expression of renin-binding protein and renin in the kidneys of rats with two-kidney one-clip hypertension. *J Hypertens*. 2000;18(7):935-43.
15. Agrawal A, Rachleff VM, Travaglini KJ, Mukherjee S, Crane P, Hawrylycz M, et al. Hierarchical Bayesian inference to model continuous phenotypical progression in Alzheimer's Disease. *bioRxiv*. 2024.
16. van Bilsen JHM, Dulos R, van Stee MF, Meima MY, Rouhani Rankouhi T, Neergaard Jacobsen L, et al. Seeking Windows of Opportunity to Shape Lifelong Immune Health: A Network-Based Strategy to Predict and Prioritize Markers of Early Life Immune Modulation. *Front Immunol*. 2020;11:644.
17. Lapteva N, Nieda M, Ando Y, Ide K, Hatta-Ohashi Y, Dymshits G, et al. Expression of renin-angiotensin system genes in immature and mature dendritic cells identified using human cDNA microarray. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 2001;285(4):1059-65.
18. Prata DP, Costa-Neves B, Cosme G, Vassos E. Unravelling the genetic basis of schizophrenia and bipolar disorder with GWAS: A systematic review. *J Psychiatr Res*. 2019;114:178-207.
19. Wong EH, So HC, Li M, Wang Q, Butler AW, Paul B, et al. Common variants on Xq28 conferring risk of schizophrenia in Han Chinese. *Schizophr Bull*. 2014;40(4):777-86.
20. Tian F, Liu D, Chen J, Liao W, Gong W, Huang R, et al. Proteomic Response of Rat Pituitary Under Chronic Mild Stress Reveals Insights Into Vulnerability and Resistance to Anxiety or Depression. *Front Genet*. 2021;12:751999.

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